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1.0 Introduction

1.1 Overview of John Deere in the Agriculture Sector

Figure 1: *John Deere Logo (UpMeTomorrow, 2018)*

John Deere, officially known as Deere & Company, is a major American brand and manufacturer of farm machinery, agricultural, construction, and industrial forestry equipment. It was founded by John Deere in 1837. It is headquartered in Moline, Illinois. Over the years, John Deere has embraced modern technologies to support the digital transformation of agriculture. The company is renowned for its innovative farming equipment, such as GPS-enabled tractors, vehicles, harvesting tools, precision agriculture tools, etc, which are considered to support sustainable farming by enabling farmers to produce less waste and protecting the environment and the earth. (Tikkanen, 2024; Deere Company, 2024)

Figure 2: *John Deere Today's Stats Employees (Deere Company, 2023)*

Today, John Deere employs nearly 82,200 full-time employees across over 100 locations worldwide. As of 2024, John Deere reached \$7.1 billion in net income (PRNewswire, 2024). Such a large company, of course it has a lot of information that needs to be stored together, which makes it a must to organize its data in the most correct way (Deere Company, 2023). This information we called it as Big Data, which must be accessed, modified, and stored in a safe place using Big Data Technologies and Tools. We will discuss further in the next section.

The term Big Data has multiple definitions that can be found on the internet. According to Google Cloud, Big Data is a tools that help to deal with complex data to extract value from the data (Cloud, 2025). Meanwhile, Oracle defines Big Data as extremely large and complex data that cannot be easily managed with traditional processing tools (Chen, 2024). When a data-related problem cannot be solved by a relational database, it is typically classified as a Big Data problem. This explanation greatly oversimplifies what Big Data is.

John Deere is among the most well-known companies in the agriculture sector to have implemented Big Data Technologies. The company integrates IoT sensors, GPS, satellite data, and AI systems in tractors that can monitor soil health, crop conditions, and weather predictions in real time. After that, the data is then transferred to the John Deere Operations Center, where it can be analyzed, providing support and advice to the farmers that can improve their operations in agriculture for the future (Persson, 2024; Findaso, 2023).

1.2 The Role of Big Data in Agricultural Productivity & Decision-Making

The purpose of this research paper is to discuss the role of Big Data Technologies and Tools in analyzing real-world applications in the context of agricultural productivity and decision-making. Agriculture has become data-driven with the rise of digital technology, depending on real-time data to increase its efficiency and sustainability (Trace X Technologies, 2023).

Figure 3: *John Deere GPS-Enabled Devices*

John Deere uses modern farming equipment such as sensors, computers, and transportation systems like trucks to generate big amounts of data, which comes from GPS-enabled devices, including weather predictions, soil health, and crop conditions.

However, traditional computers are struggling to process and analyze the information, which can be time-consuming.

Agriculture, one of the oldest of human activities, is transforming in the digital era. The advancement of technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), automation, transportation vehicles, machines, and Big Data Analytics has enabled humans to live more intelligently. Traditional agriculture is increasingly supported by decision-making based on massive data, from predicting the weather to monitoring the soil health (Admin, 2025). This shows that Big Data plays an important part in enhancing agricultural performance.

Big Data is important for storing a large amount of information. Applications related to estimations or crop production, land mapping, weather forecasting, crop condition, etc, require large amounts of data that traditional computation can't handle. Moreover, some of the applications, such as diseases of plants, require high reliability of data. But Big Data is suitable for this. It enables faster processing and accurate results compared to traditional computing, so that farmers can utilise this information to make better decisions, improve their agriculture, reduce waste, and improve crop condition. Below are some key ways it contributes to decision-making and improves productivity.

1. Precision Farming

Data-driven agriculture enables precision farming, and Big Data allows farmers to monitor their fields and inputs like fertilizers, pesticides, waters, and seeds. This leads to reduced costs, time efficiency, and better resource management. Like using GPS for soil sensors, which provide real-time data and soil moisture levels, it assists farmers in deciding where to apply more fertilizer in different areas. This has the potential to increase yields and also increase productivity for the farmers (Admin, 2025; Trace X Technologies, 2023).

2. Crop Health Monitoring

Figure 4: *John Deere Crop Health Monitoring System (Osborn, 2022)*

Real-time data from the sensors of the camera trucks can detect diseases or a lack of nutrients in crops early. This enables immediate action to reduce crop loss. Farmers usually receive alerts from the AI device systems that analyze images received from sensors to detect early signs of disease. Early detection can help prevent large-scale crop loss, maintain the crop's health, and maintain the yield condition, which results in overall crop productivity and reduces damage. Furthermore, Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) help predict crop disease. Such models deal with noisy, a variety of data, and Big Data can effectively learn and predict the disease easily in a short amount of time (Prakasa Rao, 2021; Admin, 2025).

3. Climate Resilience

Data-driven agriculture helps farmers adapt to climate patterns by providing data on weather patterns. This information can guide the farmers to predict and prepare for something before it happens, such as planting schedules, crop selection, and management strategies, which enables farmers to prepare against extreme weather. With the use of predictive analysis, farmers can make decisions to mitigate the risks of climate change, like storms, floods, etc. These strategies also indirectly contribute to long-term productivity by minimizing the impact despite the challenges (Trace X Technologies, 2023).

4. Irrigation Systems

Agriculture consumes a major portion of water. However, climate change and changes in rainfall can create problems. Traditional farming methods can't adapt well to those problems. By using smart irrigation systems in sensors and data (Like soil moisture, weather, temperature, etc), it can forecast when water is needed, avoid overwatering and underwatering, can schedule more efficiently, and make better decisions for farmers when dealing with water shortages. This use of smart irrigation is an example of Big Data improving the decision-making of the farmer and also increasing productivity in agriculture.

Overall, Big Data plays a critical role in helping farmers for their agriculture safer. Help them make smarter decisions, improve productivity, and ensure more sustainable agriculture in this modern day.

2.0 Data Source & Acquisition

2.1 Use Case

First, we will discuss the Use Case. This paper focuses on predicting crop yield, enhancing it, and also helps them to increase efficiency and productivity for the farmer. By collecting and analyzing data using Big Data Technologies and Tools, farmers can make better decisions for their own farms. To support this Use Case, various types of datasets are required. A detailed breakdown of the suitable dataset will be listed and explained below.

2.2 Reasoning of Data

The reason behind selecting those datasets is that we saw they contained the information that we wanted to enhance crop yield, precision, decision-making, productivity, and farm efficiency for the farmers. We have to apply Big Data Technologies to analyze the agricultural data. Therefore, this dataset fulfills our criteria for a dataset needed for this research experiment.

2.3 List & Description of Data

The dataset used in these practicals was taken from Kaggle, a platform that provides an open-source dataset collection. So, for my practical, to get to guarantee a detailed analysis, I selected 2 agriculture datasets from Kaggle. Requirements for precision agriculture, which is in crop yield, were suitable for both datasets. The first dataset was uploaded into the Kaggle website by Atharva Soundankar (2024), called “Smart Farming Sensor Data for Yield Prediction”, and the second dataset was uploaded by Muhammad Waqar Azam (2022), called “Agricultural Crops Image Classification” (Soundankar, 2024; Azam, 2022).

So, the first dataset, which is “Smart Farming Sensor Data for Yield Prediction”, contains 1 file. The file is called “Smart_Farming_Crop_Yield_2024”, contains 501 rows and 22 columns from 2024. It has 22 attributes, which are discussed in the table below. The dataset consists of several information, namely farm_id, region, crop_type, soil_moisture_%, soil_pH, temperature_C, rainfall_mm, humidity_%, sunlight_hours, irrigation_type, fertilizer_type, pesticide_usage_ml, sowing_date, harvest_date, total_days, yield_kg_per_hectare, sensor_id, timestamp, latitude, longitude, NDVI_index, and crop_disease_status (Soundankar, 2024; Azam, 2022).

Table 1. *Description of the File First Dataset (Soundankar, 2024)*

Name	Description	Example
farm_id	Unique number for each farm.	FARM0001
region	Region for each farm.	North India

crop_type	Type of crop on the farm.	Wheat
soil_moisture_%	Soil moisture in percentage to see how good it is. In percentage.	35.95
soil_pH	Soil pH level, usually around (5.5-7.5).	5.99
temperature_C	Average temperature during the crop season (°C).	17.79
rainfall_mm	Total rainfall in mm.	75.62
humidity_%	Average humidity in percentage.	77.03
sunlight_hours	Average sunlight hours per day.	7.27
irrigation_type	Type of irrigation, such as Drip, Sprinkler, etc.	None
fertilizer_type	Type of fertilizer, such as Organic, Inorganic, etc.	Organic

pesticide_usage_ml	Daily pesticide usage in millimeters.	6.34
sowing_date	The date when the crop was sown by the farmer.	1/8/2024
harvest_date	Date when the crop was harvested.	5/9/2024
total_days	Total days from the first until the end, usually for crop growth time.	122
yield_kg_per_hectare	Crop yield is how much weight. Based on kilograms per hectare.	4408.07
sensor_id	ID of the IoT sensor when they send the data report about the crop.	SENS0001
timestamp	The time when the sensor takes a snapshot.	3/19/2024
latitude	Farm Location (East & West) & (Range: 10.0 -	14.970941

	35.0).	
longitude	Farm Location (North & South) & (Range: 70.0 - 90.0).	82.997689
NDVI_index	Stands for Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (Range: 0.3 - 0.9).	0.63
crop_disease_status	Crop disease status, such as Mild, Moderate, etc.	Mild

Each name and type of dataset leads to a more comprehensive understanding of the precision agriculture in enhancing crop yield and farm efficiency. Last but not least, the second dataset is “Agricultural Crops Image Classification”. The dataset contains 30 directories, and each of the folders has its own pictures. The 30 directories are Cherry, Coffee-plant, Cucumber, Fox_nut (Makhana), Lemon, Olive-tree, Pearl_millet (Bajra), Tobacco-plant, almond, banana, cardamom, chili, clove, coconut, cotton, gram, jowar, jute, maize, mustard-oil, papaya, pineapple, rice, soyabean, sugarcane, sunflower, tea, tomato, vigna-radiati (Mung), and wheat (Azam, 2022).

Table 2. *Description of the Folders Second Dataset (Azam, 2022)*

Name of the Folder	Amount
Cherry	32 Pictures

Coffee-plant	29 Pictures
Cucumber	31 Pictures
Fox_nut (Makhana)	23 Pictures
Lemon	28 Pictures
Olive-tree	30 Pictures
Pearl millet (Bajra)	39 Pictures
Tobacco-plant	33 Pictures
almond	21 Pictures
banana	31 Pictures
cardamom	22 Pictures
chili	23 Pictures
clove	30 Pictures

coconut	25 Pictures
cotton	32 Pictures
gram	25 Pictures
jowar	30 Pictures
jute	23 Pictures
maize	31 Pictures
mustard-oil	28 Pictures
papaya	23 Pictures
pineapple	25 Pictures
rice	29 Pictures
soyabean	30 Pictures
sugarcane	25 Pictures

sunflower	24 Pictures
tea	23 Pictures
tomato	26 Pictures
vigna-radiati (Mung)	27 Pictures
wheat	31 Pictures

2.4 Data Source

In today's era of smart agriculture, farming isn't all about crops, soil, and yield; it's also about data itself. Companies like John Deere are also transforming from traditional agriculture to smart agriculture, such as water harvesting (Collecting and storing rainwater) to machine and technology, such as GPS, IoT sensors, and satellite imagery. These technologies collect massive amounts of data coming from the devices in real time, which allows the farmers to be more productive and smarter in decision-making.

In this section, we have to mention what problem is the issue of data collection is, what sources are used to gather the data, what the possible challenges are with collecting the data from the mentioned sources, and suggest what Big Data Tools and Technologies can be used for this case. These types of applications rely on 4 primary data sources to support and deliver it's analytics. Each provides different explanations and insights into farming operations:

1. GPS-Enabled

Figure 5. *Example of GPS-Enabled Devices (Hall, 2020)*

Figure 6. *Example of StarFire GPS (Case, 2021)*

John Deere began integrating a GPS system into its tractors in 1999, which marked a turning point for John Deere in tractor accuracy. Now, the company equips its tractors with high-precision GPS, which can achieve an accuracy of 2.5 centimeters (Blackman, 2021). This level of precision is made possible through the use of StarFire GPS, which relies the data from the satellites by NASA and Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL). Doing this enables the

system to achieve perfect accuracy as it connects to the satellites. These GPS allow them to collect detailed location and planting coordinates (Seeds or Crops). This improves efficiency, reduces time-consuming tasks, and increases the crop yield while minimizing input waste (Case, 2021; Hall, 2020).

2. IoT Sensors

Figure 7. *Example of IoT Sensors in Irrigation Systems (Chalimov, 2023)*

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a network that describes the network of objects embedded with sensors and other technologies. The purpose is to connect and exchange data with other devices over the internet. So, in the context of agriculture, farm equipment uses a device to combine IoT sensors that track real-time soil. These sensors are connected to their tractors, enabling the farmer to monitor in a short amount of time. Then, it goes to the Big Data tools such as Apache Kafka to process and analyze this data efficiently. It tracks the soil health and the weather temperature alongside pH levels, which helps the farmer improve their decision-making. The future of smart agriculture, especially IoT sensors, must involve real-time soil observation through online systems for each agricultural application (Findaso, 2023; Oracle, 2020).

3. Satellite Imagery

Figure 8. Example of Satellite Imagery Devices (Innovations, 2023)

John Deere enhances its precision agriculture capabilities by leveraging satellite imagery and satellite-enabled communication systems. In order to achieve this, John Deere has partnered with SpaceX, utilizing its Starlink Satellite, where the internet is much more reliable and faster in rural farming areas. By using this solution, John Deere installed ruggedized Starlink in the tractor machine, paired with 4G LTE JDLINK modems to even further provide seamless connectivity to the equipment to the John Deere Operations Center (A centralized platform that supports more than 250 agricultural software applications) (Deere, 2024; Jewett, 2022). This satellite-enabled connection allows farmers to have access to real-time data, predictive maintenance, and automated decision-making tools. So, by combining high-resolution satellite imagery with IoT, John Deere helps farmers monitor crop health, reduce downtime, perform remote diagnostics, and predictive maintenance workloads, as well as being suitable for farmers even in areas with limited WiFi coverage (Tomás, 2024).

4. Weather Forecasting

Figure 9. *GreemStar™ 2 Devices (Deere, 2025a)*

John Deere helps farmers stay ahead of the weather with its Mobile Weather System, which is a smart sensor that is mounted on the tractor machine and integrated with GreemStar™ 2 & 3. This equipment is to collect real-time weather data like temperature, wind speed, the direction of the wind, humidity, surroundings, and something called Delta T, which is a key to measure that tells you if it's the right time to spray or not. By using this equipment, farmers can make fast, informed decisions to protect their crops as well as avoid any risky conditions that can damage their crops. And also, all the data that is processed inside the Mobile Weather System will get saved and synced with tools like John Deere Operations Center and APEX Software (Deere, 2025b; Spike, 2025).

2.5 Challenges Faced with this Data

The challenges that John Deere faces involve handling a large amount of data from satellite imagery, IoT soil sensors, weather APIs, and farm equipment to give precise farming recommendations. Even so, getting the data is a real challenge because of heterogeneity, variety, velocity, quality, connectivity, and volume. Imagine that satellite imagery is only accessible to authorized people, as well as the file types being varied. Such issues make it difficult for communications, inform about things like yield prediction, and also process the data into the systems. This section highlights these challenges, their effect on John Deere

operations, and their relevance to Big Data in agriculture (Deere, 2025c; likebupt, 2024; Abdipour Chenarestansofla, 2022).

2.5.1 Data Heterogeneity

Figure 10. Example of GeoTIFF Format for a Picture (OriginLab, 2022)

Data Heterogeneity refers to differences in data formats, structures, and the process by which the data is generated (Noroozi & Mostafa, 2023). So, John Deere provides its data in a variety of formats, which poses a challenge for bringing them together, like GPS tractors, satellite images, weather stations, and IoT sensors. Like satellite image is in GeoTIFF format (Deere, 2025d), weather data is in JSON (Deere, 2025d), equipment logs are done in CSV (Deere, 2025d), and IoT sensor readings are in their own proprietary format.

Because each of them has its own “data language/format”, it’s not easy to bring everything together as one, especially for analysis. This can slow down how quickly the system delivers useful insights to the farmers. For example, being a farmer trying to match real-time soil moisture readings with satellite images that show crop health, it’s

time-consuming and also the effort to get the data in the same line. This Heterogeneity makes it hard for John Deere to deliver seamless insights to the farmers and also the field in agriculture Big Data integration (Abdipour Chenarestansofla, 2022).

2.5.1.1 Data Variety

Figure 11. *3Vs of Big Data Technologies (Lutkevich & Wigmore, 2023)*

Data Variety in Big Data exists in different formats (Such as structured, unstructured, and semi-structured data), but we need this data to be standardized or changed to a format to maximize efficiency. For example, structured data can be found in GPS coordinates. Semi-structured data, like IoT sensors in JSON format from weather services. Meanwhile, unstructured data like satellite images in GeoTIFF are also important components of variety. So, integrating these different data formats into a system is quite challenging. Therefore, it's more efficient if we standardize it first and process and use it effectively in John Deere's analytics systems (Abdipour Chenarestansofla, 2022; Bellon-Maurel et al., 2022).

2.5.1.2 Data Velocity

Data Velocity in Big Data refers to the rapid flow and instant processing of information coming from farm equipment, IoT sensors, etc. John Deere's advanced platform ingests millions of sensor readings per second. For example, GPS-guided combines can

generate thousands of data points per second. Meanwhile, for weather and soil sensors, it can continuously update on conditions like moisture or temperature nearby multiple times per minute. Or they add more sensors, too, which is good but expensive.

Figure 12. *Apache Flink Logo (Baer, 2017)*

Usually, the company uses real-time streaming architectures like Apache Kafka and Apache Flink for the real-time streaming process. These technologies are designed to process high-speed data and analyze high volumes of data with minimal delay. If this infrastructure slows down, it can affect the outcome and opportunities. John Deere's solution ensures that data arrives fast enough so that it can update the decisions immediately, enhancing both efficiency and yield (Akanbi, 2020; Waehner, 2024; Finch & Nienhuis, 2019; Flink Forward, 2019; Milvus, 2025).

2.5.1.3 Data Quality

Data accuracy is important; it needs good data, especially for systems during processing. But still, it is difficult since there's an issue, especially in agriculture. For example, John Deere's satellite images can be taken from the satellite, but as you can see, it can be blocked by a cloud, making it hard to tell if crops are healthy or not. Sometimes, IoT sensors in the field can show the wrong values, like saying the soil is too dry when it's actually fine. These issues can mess up irrigation or lead to bad outcomes decision-making.

That's why John Deere has to verify it first before using the data. Still, it is essential to ensure that for accurate decision-making and analysis is of good quality (Jiang et al., 2019).

2.5.1.4 Connectivity

As you can see, most farmers find themselves in rural areas where they can't receive internet, thus they can't use a system like IoT sensors, equipment devices, etc. IoT sensors and any other devices require a stable and strong internet connection to send the data that they scan to the Cloud, such as soil. And also, a network outage can be the second reason that can affect the device connection as well. This connectivity poses a challenge most in rural areas or areas with high problem connections, thereby restricting John Deere's ability to offer real-time functionality.

2.5.1.5 Data Volume

Figure 13. *Apache Hadoop Logo (Wikipedia, 2016)*

Figure 14. *AWS Cloud Logo (Olumuyiwa, 2020)*

John Deere sources generate a huge amount of data through connected technologies like JDLink. This data, which includes crop health and operational details, is collected and processed to improve efficiency and productivity for farmers. But it might trouble the storage and processing systems. For example, a single smart tractor can generate gigabytes of data and sensors per day. When scaled across thousands of machines and farms, it can reach terabytes, which is heavier than gigabytes. It's not even including the satellite images, which, if we add, can get overwhelmed. To handle this, John Deere has to rely on cloud infrastructure and distributed processing tools such as AWS Cloud and Apache Hadoop to store and analyze the data efficiently and not time-consuming. However, it still by doing requires high expenses (Deere Company, 2023; Abdipour Chenarestansofla, 2022; DeGrasse, 2023).

2.6 Big Data Tools and Technologies for Real-Time & Batch Data Collection

In modern precision agriculture, collecting data efficiently is just as important as analyzing it. With the rise of smart farming technologies like IoT sensors, satellite systems, etc, data can be generated in a big volumes and continuously. To manage this, 2 types of data collection approaches are introduced: Real-Time and Batch.

Real-Time Data Collection, information that becomes reachable immediately after it's created. Real-Time Data is crucial for sensitive tasks like customer interactions and real-time analytics, which can provide instant outcomes. Unlike Historical Data, which depends on past data, Real-Time Data is more into immediate action, which can give an outcome right away (Amazon, 2025a; Lockwood, 2024).

On the other hand, Batch Data Collection is a method of processing data where a collection of records, or what we call "batches", is processed together at a scheduled time. It's more suitable for handling a large volume at the same time, and a scene where an immediate outcome is not urgent and needed directly (Amazon, 2025). Moving forward, choosing the right tools for each method can ensure farming becomes more efficient and accurate.

2.6.1 Big Data Tools and Technologies for Real-Time Data Collection

2.6.1.1 Apache Kafka

Figure 15. *Apache Kafka Logo (it-novum, 2024)*

An open-source platform called Apache Kafka is a platform used for distributed data, consuming, and processing streaming data in real-time. Streaming data is continuously created from any system, and it starts from one to thousands of data sources, and is sent to the data at the same time. This shows that Kafka is designed to handle high-throughput and low-latency internet data streams (Amazon, 2025a).

Furthermore, Kafka is widely used for constructing data pipelines and specific domain streaming applications in areas like healthcare, financial, and agriculture. It is strong at collecting, processing, and distributing data streams like continuous stream of sensor readings or Application Programming Interface (API). This shows that it is flexible and can be used for any areas including agriculture (Flinders, 2024; Amazon, 2025a).

Figure 16. *Creator of Apache Kafka, Jay Kreps (Center), with co-founders Jun Rao (Left) & Neha Narkhede (Right) (Harris, 2015)*

Originally, Kafka was developed by LinkedIn and announced globally in 2011. It was created by Jay Kreps, Neha Narkhede, and Jun Rao, who created Kafka to handle the high volume of data generated by LinkedIn's infrastructure (Ahmed, 2019). Kafka provides 3 main functions for users who use it:

1. It enables applications to publish data.
 - For example, think of an app that tries to send a message to Kafka. A soil sensor detects that the field is too dry, and it publishes the data to Kafka, which is from the sensors, and now Kafka can read and process the data.
2. It effectively stores records in the order in which records were generated.
 - Kafka keeps the messages in the order of the queue in which they were received at that time.
3. It processes records in real-time.
 - Now, Kafka can handle the data as it comes in, without waiting. So it can process the real-time data continuously, it's like a smart computer that never sleeps, it keeps processing 24/7 (IBM, 2021; Amazon, 2025a).

-Architecture & Key Components

Figure 17. *Apache Kafka Architecture Diagram (GeeksforGeeks, 2025)*

1. **Kafka Cluster:** A distributed system that consists of multiple Kafka Brokers working together that handle storage and processing it which is a real-time streaming data. This is useful when handling large-scale applications like those in healthcare, agriculture, and so on.
2. **Brokers:** Servers inside the Kafka Cluster. It is responsible for storing data, or we can say it is a storage. In the case of John Deere, brokers deal with a flow of soil moisture data from thousands of sensors placed on farms.
3. **Partition:** Topics are divided into Partitions. So each Partitions start from 0, and the order follows a sequence. This Partition allows Kafka to scale horizontally by distributing data to other Brokers.
4. **Producers:** Clients that write data to the Kafka Cluster. They send data records, or we call it history, to the appropriate Partition.
5. **Consumers:** Client applications that subscribe to Kafka. Usually, Consumers or Consumers Group read and process messages from the Partition. Consumers are the

crucial part of Kafka since it enables applications to consume data streams for analytics and real-time processing.

6. Zookeeper: Zookeeper is like a security guard in Kafka. The purpose of Zookeeper is to maintain configuration information, naming, and provide group services. Usually, in Kafka, Zookeeper is used for managing Kafka Brokers.
7. Offset: Offset is like a message inside the Partition. If you look at the picture, you can't see it, but actually, Offset is located inside the Partition. The purpose of Offset is to help customers keep track of which messages they've already read and when they will continue them (GeeksforGeeks, 2025).

2.6.1.2 Apache Flink

Figure 18. *Apache Flink Logo (Baer, 2017)*

An open-source platform called Apache Flink is a distributed engine for processing streaming (Real-time) and batch data sets. Stream processing applications are designed to run continuously with minimal delay and traffic. This shows that Flink is designed to handle low-latency processing, for high availability, and remove single points of failure to ensure correctness (AWS, 2025).

Furthermore, Flink is widely used for processing large amounts of data in real-time. During the data streaming process, it connects to Apache Kafka and reads data from the

queue to process it in an ordered and continuous manner. As a stream processing engine, it complements the queue because it can process the data one at a time, which is suitable for such cases where it requires a high level of granularity for identifying patterns. This shows that it is flexible and can be used in any area, including agriculture, where both real-time and batch data are beneficial. Even companies across different industries also use Flink, like Amazon, Alibaba, eBay, etc (Hazelcast, 2024).

Figure 19. *Stratosphere Project Logo (Li Yu, 2021)*

Flink originally came from a university research project called “Stratosphere Project” in Berlin called Technische Universität Berlin in 2009. So, this Stratosphere Project is a project made by Germans that focuses on developing new generations of Big Data tools and analytics platforms. One of their ideas, or original project idea, was Flink. The Apache Flink Community, a division of the Apache Software Foundation (ASF), developed Flink at that time. And, in 2014, they changed the name to Apache Flink, which soon will be renowned worldwide (Apache Flink Community, 2024; Li Yu, 2021).

Figure 20. *Alibaba Company Logo (Fan, 2024)*

In 2016, the first company to use Flink was Alibaba Group. It is the most significant contribution company that uses Flink at that time. Since Alibaba Group experienced rapid growth, it has led to an increase in data on its e-commerce platform called Alibaba. So, in order to ensure the capability of processing data in a real-time situation, they choose Flink as their streaming technology. As a result, in 2016, Flink was announced to be deployed in large-scale production for all users, and in 2016, Flink released their first version (Apache Flink Community, 2024; Li Yu, 2021).

-Architecture & Key Components

Figure 21. Apache Flink Architecture Diagram (Huang et al., 2022)

1. Job Manager: Job Manager acts as the master system running in a Flink area and is responsible for scheduling tasks, coordinating, ensuring fault tolerance, and executing strategies. There are 2 types of managers, Job and Task Managers.
2. Task Manager: Job Manager is more into accepting the task, while Task Manager is more into executing the task. Task Manager is a worker process on each slave node that provides resources for the execution of the tasks in Flink.
3. Scheduler: Manage the task manager and give them tasks to the task managers to execute the data.

4. Checkpoint Coordinator: Continue operating without any interruption.
5. Task Manager (Task Manager 1, 2, and 3): It also contains the components that are responsible for memory management.
6. Flink Program: We define the data sources, identify the operations on the input data, identify the flow between the data and the operators, and send the data out to one or more destinations.
7. Optimizer: Optimize the application from the execution perspective.
8. Network Manager: Coordinate and communicate data among the Task Manager (Sharma, 2021; Gębiś, 2024; Huang et al., 2022).

2.6.1.3 Apache NiFi

Figure 22. *Apache NiFi Logo (Wikimedia, 2023)*

As complexity in data processing tasks increases across organizations, there is a higher demand for the use of Big Data Tools. Therefore, the following is the goal of this paper is to provide a close look at Apache NiFi. NiFi is an open-source tool for data integration and a data flow automation platform that enables users to manage the flow of data between systems. It is strong for handling both real-time and batch data, depending on the use case and situation we want to use it for.

Usually, the basic principles of NiFi are thoroughly described, with special placed on its User Interface (UI). Furthermore, NiFi is widely used in finance, telecommunications, IoT,

agriculture, and Big Data sectors. NiFi is used for real-time data processing, real-time capturing, ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) operations, and data tracking. This shows that by applying Apache NiFi, it can achieve lower system downtime, real-time integration like sensors, and easy-to-use (dremio, 2024; Melby T, 2024; Carder, 2021; DATAVOLO, 2024). Well, in addition to the tools above, Apache Hadoop is a well-known tool which is focusing on batch data collection. It is used for analyzing large sets of historical data across distribution systems.

Figure 23. Example of Web User Interface (UI) of Apache NiFi (Wikipedia Contributors, 2025)

NiFi was created by the US National Security Agency (NSA) under the project name “NiagaraFiles” in 2006. The reason why the NSA developed this software is to manage large volumes of unstructured data, including ingesting and analyzing it in real-time. In 2014, the NSA donated code that they had developed to the Apache Software Foundation to make it open source. Since then, all users have widely used this open source for data pipeline automation, which is in the engineering field (Melby T, 2024; dremio, 2024; DATAVOLO, 2024).

-Architecture & Key Components

Figure 24. *Apache NiFi Architecture Diagram (Apache NiFi Team, 2025)*

1. OS/Host: The User's laptop device system when accessing Apache NiFi.
2. Java Virtual Machine (JVM): NiFi executes within a JVM on a host operating system.
3. Web Server: Is to provide NiFi's Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) based command and control APIs.
4. Flow Controller: Flow Controller is the brain of all software in Flink. It controls the timing of when extensions collect all the resources to run and supplies threads for them to use.
5. Processors: Systems that perform the work.
6. Extension: Extension is used to operate and execute the data within the JVM.
7. FlowFile Repository: A place where NiFi records the current status of its knowledge about FlowFile, which is stored in the FlowFile Repository.
8. Content Repository: A place where the actual content of a FlowFile lives. Usually, it is used for storing the actual content (data) of FlowFiles.
9. Provenance Repository: A place where all the data is stored. It is different from Content Repository, where Provenance is more into data, while Content is more into the content of the data (Apache NiFi Team, 2025; Carder, 2021).

3.0 Dataset Introduction

To support the agriculture use case on predicting crop yields, enhancing it, and helping them to increase efficiency and productivity, we use the “Smart Farming Sensor Data for Yield Prediction” dataset by Atharva Soundankar (2024), which can be found on Kaggle, which serves as our main dataset for our analysis. The second dataset will be introduced later, after this explanation, to support the primary dataset (Soundankar, 2024).

This first dataset provides more sensor data from farming yields, essentials for crop monitoring, and yield prediction, since it contains numbers. The reason why this first dataset was selected as our main topic is that it includes diverse types of data, like crop types, farm conditions in percentage form, environmental factors, the day when the crop is harvested, location, and crop status (Soundankar, 2024).

Below is the dataset attribute for the first dataset.

3.1 Dataset Format (First Dataset)

Table 3. *Description of the Dataset Format: First Dataset (Soundankar, 2024)*

File Name	Description
File Name	Smart_Farming_Crop_Yield_2024.csv
File Format	CSV (Comma-Separated Values).
Structure	Tabular format (Rows & Columns).
Rows	501

Columns	22
File Size	130 KiloByte.
Missing Values	None.
Duplicates Values	None.

3.2 Dataset Type (First Dataset)

Table 4. *Description of the Dataset Type: First Dataset (Soundankar, 2024)*

Attribute	Dataset Type
farm_id	Integer or String
region	String
crop_type	Categorical or String
soil_moisture_%	Float
soil_pH	Float
temperature_C	Float

rainfall_mm	Float
humidity_%	Float
sunlight_hours	Float
irrigation_type	Categorical or String
fertilizer_type	Categorical or String
pesticide_usage_ml	Float
sowing_date	Date
harvest_date	Date
total_days	Integer
yield_kg_per_hectare	Float
sensor_id	Integer or String
timestamp	DateTime

latitude	Float
longitude	Float
NDVI_index	Float
crop_disease_status	Categorical or String

3.3 Example Data Collected (First Dataset)

This is an example of how the actual data collected or the outcome.

Table 5. *Description of the Example Data Collected: First Dataset (Soundankar, 2024)*

Attribute	Example
farm_id	FARM0001
region	North India
crop_type	Wheat
soil_moisture_%	35.95
soil_pH	5.99

temperature_C	17.79
rainfall_mm	75.62
humidity_%	77.03
sunlight_hours	7.27
irrigation_type	None
fertilizer_type	Organic
pesticide_usage_ml	6.34
sowing_date	1/8/2024
harvest_date	5/9/2024
total_days	122
yield_kg_per_hectare	4408.07
sensor_id	SENS0001

timestamp	3/19/2024
latitude	14.970941
longitude	82.997689
NDVI_index	0.63
crop_disease_status	Mild

3.4 Dataset Format (Second Dataset)

Going to the second dataset, we use Muhammad Waquar Azam’s (2022) “Agricultural Crops Image Classification” dataset, which is available on Kaggle. For our analysis, it serves as our supporting dataset. This second dataset contains pictures related to agriculture, which the first dataset doesn’t have, like plants, vegetables, flowers, etc. All of the pictures are taken from IoT sensors, GPS-enabled devices, satellite images, and smart farming tools. For example, a modern tractor has devices that monitor soil and crop health in real time. This helps show how technology supports precision farming through image-based (Azam, 2022).

Below is the dataset attribute for the second dataset (Azam, 2022).

Table 6. *Description of the Dataset Format: Second Dataset (Azam, 2022)*

File Name	Description
File Name	Agricultural-crops.csv

File Format	-Image folders.
Structure	-30 folders. -Joint Photographic Experts Group (JPEG) or Joint Photographic Group (JPG) Files. -Portable Network Graphics (PNG) Files.
File Size	83.22 MegaByte.

3.5 Dataset Type (Second Dataset)

Table 7. *Description of the Dataset Type: Second Dataset (Azam, 2022)*

Attribute	Dataset Type
almond	-3 PNG Files. -18 JPG Files. -Binary File (Image Data).
banana	-1 JPEG Files. -2 PNG Files. -29 JPG Files. -Binary File (Image Data).

cardamom	-8 JPG Files. -14 JPEG Files. -Binary File (Image Data).
Cherry	-14 JPEG Files. -18 JPG Files. -Binary File (Image Data).
chilli	-23 JPEG Files. -Binary File (Image Data).
clove	-15 JPEG & JPG Files. -Binary File (Image Data).
coconut	-5 JPEG Files. -20 JPG Files. -Binary File (Image Data).
Coffee-plant	-29 JPG Files. -Binary File (Image Data).
cotton	-1 PNG Files.

	<p>-2 JPEG Files.</p> <p>-29 JPG Files.</p> <p>-Binary File (Image Data).</p>
Cucumber	<p>-2 JPEG Files.</p> <p>-29 JPG Files.</p> <p>-Binary File (Image Data).</p>
Fox_nut(Makhana)	<p>-7 JPG Files.</p> <p>-16 JPEG Files.</p> <p>-Binary File (Image Data).</p>
gram	<p>-2 PNG Files.</p> <p>-8 JPEG Files.</p> <p>-15 JPG Files.</p> <p>-Binary File (Image Data).</p>
jowar	<p>-10 JPEG Files.</p> <p>-20 JPG Files.</p> <p>-Binary File (Image Data).</p>
jute	<p>-5 JPEG Files.</p>

	<p>-18 JPG Files.</p> <p>-Binary File (Image Data).</p>
Lemon	<p>-9 JPG Files.</p> <p>-19 JPEG Files.</p> <p>-Binary File (Image Data).</p>
maize	<p>-10 JPEG Files.</p> <p>-21 JPG Files.</p> <p>-Binary File (Image Data).</p>
mustard-oil	<p>-2 PNG Files.</p> <p>-8 JPEG Files.</p> <p>-18 JPG Files.</p> <p>-Binary File (Image Data).</p>
Olive-tree	<p>-1 PNG Files.</p> <p>-10 JPEG Files.</p> <p>-19 JPG Files.</p> <p>-Binary File (Image Data).</p>
papaya	<p>-1 JPEG Files.</p>

	<p>-22 JPG Files.</p> <p>-Binary File (Image Data).</p>
Pearl_millet(bajra)	<p>-1 PNG Files.</p> <p>-3 JPEG Files.</p> <p>-35 JPG Files.</p> <p>-Binary File (Image Data).</p>
pineapple	<p>-25 JPG Files.</p> <p>-Binary File (Image Data).</p>
rice	<p>-1 PNG Files.</p> <p>-12 JPEG Files.</p> <p>-29 JPG Files.</p> <p>-Binary File (Image Data).</p>
soyabean	<p>-8 JPEG Files.</p> <p>-22 JPG Files.</p> <p>-Binary File (Image Data).</p>
sugarcane	<p>-7 JPEG Files.</p> <p>-18 JPG Files.</p>

	-Binary File (Image Data).
sunflower	-1 PNG Files. -4 JPEG Files. -19 JPG Files. -Binary File (Image Data).
tea	-4 JPG Files. -19 JPEG Files. -Binary File (Image Data).
Tobacco-plant	-14 JPEG Files. -33 JPG Files. -Binary File (Image Data).
tomato	-10 JPG Files. -16 JPEG Files. -Binary File (Image Data).
vigna-radiati(Mung)	-5 JPEG Files. -22 JPG Files. -Binary File (Image Data).

wheat	-4 JPEG Files. -27 JPG Files. -Binary File (Image Data).
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3.6 Example Data Collected (Second Dataset)

Below are a few sample images from the dataset, each of which represents a different type of crop. This is an example of how the actual data collected or the outcome is.

Table 8. *Description of the Example Data Collected: Second Dataset (Azam, 2022)*

Attribute	Example
almond	
banana	

cardamom

4.0 System Architecture Diagram

4.1 Data Integration

Data Integration, a process of combining the data from all parts into one so that it can be analyzed, processed, or stored more easily. When working with Big Data, this means dealing with a large structure of data from all parts. The processing of Big Data has to be the same as organizational standards in order to ensure the reduction of risk with the data. Doing this not only helps reduce the risks but also makes the data more secure, more efficient, and useful for decision-making (Curran, 2021).

Figure 25. *Data Integration Architecture Diagram (Kutz, 2024)*

1. Ok, first, we will go to Data Sources, where it belongs. An example of the source systems can be a SQL database, like queries, Customer Relationship Management (CRM), which is from Salesforce technology, focusing on customer relationships with businesses, Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), which is a business management software for users, IoT devices like sensors, social media output like pictures in JPEG, PJG, or PNG, and files.

Figure 26. *ETL Vs ELT Process (Emilio, 2025)*

2. After that, it goes to the Staging Area, which is the ETL, or we call it Extract, Transform, and Load. This part is focusing on getting data from the place where it's originally obtained. By using ETL tools, we can connect to the data sources and collect the data that we want to use. However, in the picture we use ELT, which is Extract, Load, and Transform, where it means that it transforms data within the Data Warehouse itself (Emilio, 2025). This is similar to a tool, which is Apache NiFi.
3. The Storage Layer, which includes the Data Warehouse and Data Marts. This is a place where the data that has been processed in the ETL will be stored permanently. The Data Warehouse contains the data that we stored just now, while the Data Marts are a subset of the Data Warehouse that is designed for a specific business like areas such as marketing, which is not all areas of business.

4. From the Storage Layer goes to the Presentation Layer. There's a step that involves APIs and SQL. So, once the data is clean and stored in the Data Warehouse, the data has to be sent to the customers for further analysis, reporting, or other purposes. Structured Query Language (SQL) is used when the data needs to be directly queried from the database. At the same time, Application Programming Interface (APIs) are used for technology to connect data.

Figure 27. *How API Works (Kumawat, 2023)*

5. In the Presentation Layer, there are several tools like:
- Business Intelligence (BI) Tools: Turn data into actionable insights. Help the organizations make better decisions (Microsoft, 2025).
 - Reporting Tools: Collect, process, and analyze data from various sources, which will create a dashboard and report (Indeed Editorial Team, 2025).
 - Business Applications: The Process of combining data from various sources to create a business plan.
 - Operational Systems: Designed to support the day-to-day function of the organization.
 - So, the Presentation Layer is mostly for presenting the data (Kutz, 2024; Bartley, 2025).

4.1.1 Justification of Data Integration

Figure 28. *Example of Data Integration Diagram (Alibaba Clouder, 2020)*

The data sources, Apache Kafka, Flink, and NiFi, were found to be the best choice in agriculture, especially for John Deere, because as you can see, those can process high volumes of data in a simple time while ensuring it is fast and accurate farming decision-making.

Satellite images can detect crop health data for hundreds of kilometers, IoT devices can provide detailed results from the sensors, and APIs give forecasts and measurements about the areas. Apache Kafka can handle large amounts of real-time data, which can reduce downtime and ensure no rural network leads to losing data. Apache Flink can provide real-time stream processing, which allows instant analysis, such as soil moisture. Apache NiFi is more into the flow of data between systems, collecting the structured and unstructured data, such as CSV Format & Satellite Images.

So, by integrating all of these sources using those tools, agriculture ensures that critical insights are delivered quickly, helping to improve the crops (LUMENALTA, 2024; Bartley, 2025; Bartley, 2025).

4.1.2 Tools & Justification

1. Apache Kafka

- Streaming data from IoT sensors allows early warning about floods and so on. By having this system, it enables the system to defend John Deere data even though it is in a rural area where the internet is limited.

2. Apache NiFi

- ETL processes like correcting cloud in CSV logs, meeting the quality of John Deere.

3. Apache Flink

- Allow instant computation and transformation of incoming data, especially from IoT sensors. This will enable real-time analysis, such as checking the moisture level of the soil. This helps Flink, especially in John Deere, react quickly to the farm environment.

4.2 Data Storage

Precision in farming diagnostics, including crop prediction and also the sensors, is enabled by John Deere using data from satellites, IoT detectors, crop health, etc. Mostly Apache Kafka, Flink, and NiFi use the Cloud. If they combine it with their technology, it becomes possible to scale, make the data less heavy to analyze, and save money.

In Agriculture, most farmers use different kinds of tools to measure the data or collect data, which includes a variety of volumes, helping to update farming methods. The data includes pictures taken by satellites or sensors, which provide real-time sensor results like soil health. This kind of data may be structured, unstructured, or semi-structured, with huge quantities, often reaching gigabytes or maybe even terabytes. Organizations such as John Deere must focus more on advanced technologies to store their crucial data. Making farmers more sustainable and productive requires managing and utilising such a vast amount of data (El Mehdi El Aissi et al., 2023).

4.2.1 Analysis of Data Types & Volume

John Deere, especially all the farmers, have to know what type of data they collect, the volume when collecting the data, the format, and how fast the data is collected before making a storage design. And also, data flowing on the platform comes from multiple sources, which decides how storage is built.

Figure 29. *Types of Big Data, Data Formats In Agriculture (Singh Punn et al., 2019)*

In the previous section, we discussed the types of data formats under Data Variety. This section provides a more detailed explanation of the specific data format types.

1. Structured Data is information organized in a predefined, easily searchable format, and it usually uses rows and columns in a database (tableau, 2025).
2. Unstructured Data is information that lacks structure, making it difficult to analyze, such as images, audio, and videos (Jonker & Gomstyn, 2025). Like on a website, as you can see that most of the explanation depends on what content is to be delivered.
3. Semi-Structured Data is a combination of both Structured and Unstructured Data. It contains rows and columns, but also includes a tag like CSV Format. Examples are like Email, they contain date, subject, sender, etc, but the body or inside the email is considered as unstructured text, which keeps changing depending on the users, like the grammar, how long the information is, etc (Redis, 2024).

Now, let's connect it to John Deere agriculture.

1. GPS-Enabled & Satellite Imagery

Figure 30. *NASA Logo (Cawley, 2019)*

John Deere relies on satellite images to keep track of their tractors in order to keep track of their crop health, and also the majority of the areas. They received the data from their own GPS, which is StarFire GPS, which relies the data from the satellites by NASA and Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL). Both companies are well-known for their advanced technology, which can provide a 4K clear image and detailed views of a field. Furthermore, John Deere partnered with SpaceX, utilizing its Starlink Satellite, where the internet is faster and suitable to use in rural areas since it is paired with 4G LTE JDLink modems (Tomás, 2024; Case, 2021; Hall, 2020).

- **Type & Format:** Most of the GPS data is unstructured data. The format is in GeoTIFF format, since it stores important geographic information.
- **Volume:** There are millions of satellite images, which can be in gigabytes or terabytes. Since John Deere is a company that has been operating for a very long time, it generates

over a gigabyte or terabyte of data every week. Some of them are in batches in order to ensure efficiency, but still, they have to deal with a large amount of data.

2. IoT Sensors

By integrating IoT-enabled sensors into agriculture equipment through the John Deere device, farmers can monitor real-time soil health, such as temperature, moisture, pH, etc. These sensors make it easier to check soil conditions.

- **Type & Format:** Most of the GPS data is unstructured and semi-structured data. The format is in JavaScript Object Notation (JSON), GeoTIFF, or CSV, so it can be more simply handled and connected to the devices.
- **Volume:** This IoT sensor depends on the farmers or users when using the tractors. A farm using more than 1 sensor to capture the data is much easier than relying on 1 sensor that gathers data every single minute. At the end, it depends on the season, which can either lead to a huge amount or a small amount (Findaso, 2023; Oracle, 2020).

3. Weather Forecasting

John Deere accesses weather data to help it in predicting crop growth. They access it through their own devices called Mobile Weather System, which is a smart sensor that is mounted on the tractor machine and integrated with GreemStar™ 2 & 3. This equipment is to collect real-time weather data like temperature, wind speed, the direction of the wind, humidity, and the surroundings.

- **Type & Format:** Most of the Weather Forecasting Data is semi-structured data in JSON and CSV format.
- **Volume:** When using a Mobile Weather System (GreemStar™ 2 & 3), it consistently streams real-time data, which can forecast the weather. This can also result in either gigabytes or terabytes (Deere, 2025b; Spike, 2025).

4.2.2 Data Storage Solutions

This section discusses some of the suggested storage technologies and also mentions the solutions as to why they have been suggested in the first place so that John Deere can use it. There are 2 types of storage technologies that we can recommend:

1. Cloud Storage.
2. Hadoop Clusters.

1. Cloud Storage

Figure 31. *Google Cloud Storage Logo (Rash, 2019)*

Cloud Storage is a Cloud Computing model that enables users to store their data and files on the internet through the Cloud. The Cloud Storage function is to manage your own data storage, which gives you efficiency, durability, and scalability whenever you want to access it.

The physical storage spans multiple servers (Sometimes either in the same or different locations), and it is owned and managed by a company called Google. Google is responsible for ensuring the data is available and accessible (Ghani et al., 2020). Most of the companies,

like Amazon and Azure, also use Google Cloud as their storage to store their data, since Google Cloud is the most famous and also the most secure platform.

Figure 32. *Google Cloud Storage Architecture Diagram (Varadan, 2025)*

1. First, the process starts with the first component, which is the devices. Each users have their own devices where it is through these devices that they interact with apps, which are the Google Cloud. These devices can be either a laptop, a phone, or a tablet.
2. The next line is the App Engine, which was created by Google Cloud to scale all the applications. The function is to process what they want and send it to other components of the Cloud System.
3. There are 2 paths, Cloud PubSub and Prediction. Initially, the Cloud PubSub service enables users or data to communicate between different components of the architecture. Second, Cloud PubSub ensures that the message is delivered from the App Engine to the Cloud Dataflow for processing.
4. Cloud Dataflow is the next step after Cloud PubSub. So, it is employed for batch data processing and real-time service data processing. It processes the data from Cloud PubSub and analyzes it depending on which is required first. Then, after that, Cloud Dataflow sends the data to Cloud Datalab.
5. Cloud Datalab is a Machine Learning (ML) tool used for exploring data analysis.

6. Below Cloud Datalab is a Users and Spreadsheet. Since it comes from a Prediction, the Prediction can be stored in a Spreadsheet for documentation in the future or can be shared with other which are Users.
7. Last but not least, Prediction is an ML model that provides predictions based on the data input (Villegas-Ch et al., 2023; Amazon, 2023).

-Justification for Cloud Storage

John Deere Operations Center is using Cloud Storage for its Farm Management. Google Cloud provides high quality, availability, and scalability, which ensures the data is always available. Every day, John Deere handles a large amount of crop from IoT sensors, satellite imagery, weather data, GPS data from the tractors, customer information, etc, by using Google Cloud due to its unlimited abilities, durability for the long term, and friendly cost.

Farmers can easily access and incorporate data from various software platforms such as Google Cloud, Gemini, Apache Hadoop, etc, to help them decide when to plant the crops. These technologies also support remote diagnostics and maintenance, helping reduce equipment downtime and increasing the productivity of the farmers. Furthermore, in terms of security, Google Cloud Storage also offers strong security measures, including encryption, access controls, and compliance and regulatory checks.

This is why Cloud Storage isn't just a convenience, but it is also becoming an essential part for farmers, especially in modern agriculture. This helps farmers work smarter, faster, and more sustainably (Lee, 2025; Birch, 2024; Successive Digital, 2024).

2. Hadoop Clusters

A Hadoop Cluster is a specific kind of computing cluster made to use the Hadoop Framework for processing and storing massive amounts of data. It consists of a collection of computers, which we called it as Nodes. Hadoop enables Nodes to work with each other in order to do the processing. It also helps divide the tasks into smaller jobs, which increases efficient processing.

Hadoop Clusters are essential for handling Big Data Applications such as business, healthcare, etc. It provides a strong solution for applications that require quick and massive datasets that need to be processed. These show that Hadoop Clusters can be used in any applications (SUPERMICR, 2025). Although the terms are often used together, Hadoop refers to the software itself, whereas Hadoop Cluster is the actual setup of machines running it, or we can call as the hardware.

Figure 33. *Hadoop Clusters Architecture Diagram (Team, 2019)*

1. First, we start at the Hadoop Cluster. Hadoop Cluster represents the entire system that manages and processes data. It includes software tools like Hadoop Distributed File Systems (HDFS).

2. Going to the Core Switch, these are network devices that manage communication between Hadoop Systems and the other racks. They ensure that the connection and communication are fast and efficient, with data movement across different racks.
3. Each Racks (Rack 1, Rack 2, and Rack 3) contain multiple computers (Nodes). These nodes store data to perform processing.
4. Within each Rack, the Rack Switch handles internal communication between the nodes, which also helps connect the computers inside that rack (Brooks, 2025; Hedlund, 2011).

-Justification for Hadoop Clusters

Even though John Deere hasn't specifically mentioned that they use Hadoop Clusters, this technology is recommended for use in modern agricultural companies to handle large-scale datasets. Hadoop Clusters allow data to be stored and processed across many machines at the same time, which I can say is perfect for handling modern agriculture in information, including soil health, information regarding the yield, and also the weather.

Figure 34. Example of Walmart Apps UI (Whiteside, 2020)

In fact, other agricultural projects did use Hadoop clusters. For example, Walmart states that they used Hadoop Cluster starting from 2012 because they want data from different sources or websites into a single website so that all the unstructured like text files, images, audio, and website data, is collected into a new Hadoop version. Thanks to that,

Walmart has been speeding up all its Big Data analysis to provide the finest service, especially in the e-commerce industry. This shows that Hadoop Clusters can collect, clean, and store all different data in HDFS. Tools like Hive run SQL-like queries to find the information that we want. Even Hadoop Clusters also use Apache Pig to process messy data and make it much tidier.

However, what makes Hadoop Clusters so powerful is their ability to split Big Data into smaller tasks to run across multiple computers at once. This can speed up the analysis so that the farmer can easily scale without buying or upgrading any expensive software. John Deere is suitable for using this since John Deere faces huge data every day. It would give them faster insights, better predictions, and also stronger decision-making tools (PROJECTPRO, 2024; Kumar et al., 2022; Mewada, 2024).

4.3 Data Processing

It is efficient data processing that John Deere is the driving force behind, turning the huge and diverse volumes of data it gathers into farm-useable intelligence. This is the use of various tools and techniques to process both steps, which are Batch and Real-Time Data, which allow John Deere to do advanced analytics.

Big Data processing is a set of techniques that access large-scale data to extract useful information, especially when dealing with decision-making. Below, we will review some of the tools and techniques that are recommended or being used for Big Data analysis, which is suitable for agriculture and also for John Deere (Kumar, 2024).

4.3.1 Batch Data Processing Tools

When analyzing Big Data, batch processing is necessary for training ML models, analyzing big historical datasets, and doing calculations that are not time-sensitive. John Deere has access to several powerful batch data processing tools, such as:

1. Apache Hadoop

Apache Hadoop is a digital and meaningful framework for distributed storage, and it processes a large dataset across system clusters. It is also an open-source framework that is used to efficiently store and process large datasets, which can be terabytes or even petabytes. Apache Hadoop is well known for its storage since it can store and process a dataset in petabyte size more than a petabyte.

Compared to other Apache like Spark, Kafka, Flink, etc, Hadoop is often seen as the foundation of Big Data Processing, because it has a main component itself, which is MapReduce, which we will discuss later. Instead of using a large computer to store and process data, it also allows connecting multiple computers to analyze massive datasets in parallel, more quickly to make decisions (AWS, 2024; DigitalRoute, 2023). Below are the main components and also the important elements that make Hadoop stand out:

A. Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS)

A Distributed File System called HDFS offers application data high-throughput access. It is intended to store big files on several machines. This tool is well-suited to store archives of large quantities of historical agricultural data, years of satellite images, and weather data. What's more, every data block that HDFS has divided into smaller pieces is stored on a large number of nodes. This is to ensure the system is working perfectly, even though some of the nodes are failing.

B. MapReduce

This tool focuses on making the data as small as possible so that the system can process it faster. Imagine analyzing huge data in terabytes or even petabytes, it's gonna be time-consuming. The reason Hadoop uses MapReduce is that it is the original processing model and is integrated with HDFS. So, compared to other Apache, they're much faster than Hadoop, but Hadoop can handle big data compared to the others. So, its tools have their own uniqueness and purposes.

C. Yet Another Resource Negotiator (YARN)

YARN is the main system that controls all of the activities. YARN is used in Hadoop to manage resources and schedule tasks across the cluster. It works with MapReduce to control how jobs run, which can increase the possibility of the Hadoop ecosystem.

Using Hadoop, farmers or users get to experience far more effective utilization of commodity resources with a high availability as well as an in-built point of failure (GeeksforGeeks, 2024; Nunns, 2023).

4.3.2 Real-Time Data Processing Tools

Stream processing or real-time processing is essential when using data that comes in repeatedly and needs to be analyzed instantly to deliver instant information.

1. Apache Kafka

Apache Kafka is an open-source tool used for consuming and processing streaming data in real-time. It can handle high-throughput and low-latency internet data streams. Furthermore, it is widely used in specific domain streaming applications where data continues to be collected, like healthcare, agriculture, etc. The techniques are continuous stream of sensor readings or Application Programming Interface (API).

2. Apache Flink

Apache Flink is an open-source distributed engine for processing both real-time (Streaming) and batch data. It's designed for low-latency, high availability, and removes single points of failure to ensure correctness. Making it ideal for continuous data processing. Flink often works with Apache Kafka, reading data streams in order for real-time analysis. It can detect patterns with high granularity, which is suitable for fields like agriculture, where both real-time and batch processing are needed.

3. Apache NiFi

Apache NiFi is an open-source tool for data integration and a data flow automation platform that enables users to manage the flow of data between systems. It is strong for

handling both real-time and batch data, depending on the situation that the user wants. Mostly, it is used in finance, IoT, telecom, and agriculture for tasks like ETL, data tracking, and real-time sensor integration.

4.3.3 Tools for John Deere

1. John Deere In Field Health Monitoring

- Batch Processing: John Deere produces a large amount of satellite observations and GPS data that can be processed using Apache Kafka or Hadoop MapReduce.
- Real-Time Processing: Real-time data streams like IoT sensors for crop health, water irrigation, etc. Can be used for Apache Kafka or Apache Flink to immediately check the soil moisture, temperature, etc, to prevent bad things from disease.

2. Weather Forecasting

- Batch Processing: Might use Apache Hadoop or Apache Kafka since weather can be a lot of data during the rainy seasons, which makes Hadoop more useful, but at the same time, Kafka can be used as well on normal days or sunny days.
- Real-Time Processing: In real time, Apache Flink or Kafka Streaming can receive the data of the soil moisture sensors, weather data (Predicting rainfall), the pH surrounding, etc, so during rainfall, it can alert the farmers to stop the water machine.

3. Data Transformation

- Apache NiFi can be effective when used with Extract, Load, and Transform (ELT) or Extract, Transform, and Load (ETL). It is used to process raw data into ready-to-analyze data to analyze, ready to be stored in the Data Warehouse. Most of the researchers change or transform the file format, such as GeoTIFF satellite images, JSON, and CSV, into a normal file format like Word, PDF, etc.

5.0 Implementation & Evaluation of the Solution

In this section, we will discuss how the solution is implemented, which open-source Big Data Technologies are used. We will use Apache Spark or PySpark, which is a Python API for Apache Spark. We use a software that is a Google Colab environment. Tools like Apache Kafka are mostly used in Big Data pipelines. Our solution focuses on batch processing, which I can say Kafka is not used here.

So, for the agricultural dataset, we use the main or primary dataset, which is the “Smart Farming Sensor Data for Yield Prediction”. The second dataset of crop-related data was also used it but due to time constraints, it is intended for future work.


```
1. PySpark Setup in Google Colab

!pip install pyspark

from pyspark.sql import SparkSession

# Create a Spark Session.
spark = SparkSession.builder.appName("AgricultureAnalysis").getOrCreate()

Requirement already satisfied: pyspark in /usr/local/lib/python3.11/dist-packages (3.5.1)
Requirement already satisfied: py4j==0.10.9.7 in /usr/local/lib/python3.11/dist-packages (from pyspark) (0.10.9.7)
```

Figure 35. *Set up in Google Colab*

First, we install PySpark in Google Colab, which is the API for Apache Spark.

- “**SparkSession**”: Entry point to using Spark.
- “**.builder.appName**”: Sets the name of your Spark.
- “**.getOrCreate()**”: Create a new session if one doesn’t exist.

2. Load Dataset (CSV File)

```
import time
start_time = time.time()

# Load Dataset.
df = spark.read.csv("/content/Smart_Farming_Crop_Yield_2024.csv", header=True, inferSchema=True)

# Show the first few rows.
df.show(5)

end_time = time.time()
print("Data Loading Time: {:.2f} seconds".format(end_time - start_time))
```

```
| farm_id | region | crop_type | soil_moisture_k | soil_ph | temperature_c | rainfall_mm | humidity_k | sunlight_hours | irrigation_type | fertilizer_type | pesticide_usage_ml | sowing_date | harvest_date | total_days | yield_kg_per_hectare | sensor_id | timestamp | latitude | longitude | MOV_ind |
|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|
|FARM0001|North India|Wheat|35.95|5.99|17.79|75.62|77.83|7.27|None|Organic|6.34|2024-01-08|2024-05-09|122|4408.07|SENS0001|2024-03-19|14.978941|82.997689|0.1
|FARM0002|South USA|Soybean|19.74|7.24|30.19|89.91|81.13|5.97|Sprinkler|Inorganic|9.6|2024-02-04|2024-05-26|112|5389.98|SENS0002|2024-04-21|16.613422|78.869809|0.1
|FARM0003|South USA|Wheat|29.32|7.16|27.33|85.43|88.97|8.23|Drip|Mixed|15.95|2024-02-03|2024-06-26|144|2931.16|SENS0003|2024-02-20|19.981150|79.862286|0.1
|FARM0004|Central USA|Maize|17.33|6.03|33.73|112.01|78.46|5.83|Sprinkler|Organic|25.8|2024-02-21|2024-07-04|134|4227.8|SENS0004|2024-05-14|31.871298|85.519998|0.1
|FARM0005|Central USA|Cotton|19.37|5.92|33.86|109.09|55.73|7.93|None|Mixed|25.05|2024-02-05|2024-05-20|105|4979.96|SENS0005|2024-04-13|16.56854|81.09172|0.1
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
only showing top 5 rows
Data Loading Time: 0.65 seconds
```

Figure 36. Load Dataset (CSV File)

Then we load the dataset into PySpark and track how long it takes. It takes 17.03 seconds, which is quite normal for a huge dataset. The outcome shows the entire dataset feature and also what is inside that data.

- This starts a timer to measure how long the data loading takes.
- “**time.time()**”: Records the current time.
- “**header=True**”: Tell Spark that the first row of the CSV contains column names.
- “**inferSchema=True**”: Detects the data type of each column.
- “**df.show(5)**”: It shows the first rows of the dataset.
- “**End_time = time.time()**”: Print the total time it takes when loading the dataset, then we format it into 2 decimal places.

```
✓ [13] # Print schema to see column types.
0s df.printSchema()

⇒ root
 |-- farm_id: string (nullable = true)
 |-- region: string (nullable = true)
 |-- crop_type: string (nullable = true)
 |-- soil_moisture_%: double (nullable = true)
 |-- soil_pH: double (nullable = true)
 |-- temperature_C: double (nullable = true)
 |-- rainfall_mm: double (nullable = true)
 |-- humidity_%: double (nullable = true)
 |-- sunlight_hours: double (nullable = true)
 |-- irrigation_type: string (nullable = true)
 |-- fertilizer_type: string (nullable = true)
 |-- pesticide_usage_ml: double (nullable = true)
 |-- sowing_date: date (nullable = true)
 |-- harvest_date: date (nullable = true)
 |-- total_days: integer (nullable = true)
 |-- yield_kg_per_hectare: double (nullable = true)
 |-- sensor_id: string (nullable = true)
 |-- timestamp: date (nullable = true)
 |-- latitude: double (nullable = true)
 |-- longitude: double (nullable = true)
 |-- NDVI_index: double (nullable = true)
 |-- crop_disease_status: string (nullable = true)
```

Figure 37. *Print Scheme To See Column Types*

This code shows your data types, so you know which features you need. It also displays the structure (Schema) of your Spark DataFrame. Like “**longitude**” is “**double**” or we can call it “**Float**”. It says “**nullable = true**” means that it allows to have missing values.

```
✓ [6] # Get the number of rows.
2s num_rows = df.count()
   print(f"Number of rows: {num_rows}")

   # Get the number of columns.
   num_cols = len(df.columns)
   print(f"Number of columns: {num_cols}")

⇒ Number of rows: 500
   Number of columns: 22
```

Figure 38. Number of Rows & Columns

A code to show how many rows and columns are in the dataset.

```
3. Data Exploration

[8] from pyspark.sql.functions import col

# Display the total number of rows.
print(f"Total number of rows: {df.count()}")

# Calculate & display summary statistics for numerical columns.
print("\nSummary statistics for numerical columns:")
df.describe().show()

# 3. For each string column, display unique values.
print("\nUnique values for string columns:")
string_cols = [c for c, dtype in df.dtypes if dtype == 'string']
for col_name in string_cols:
    unique_count = df.select(col_name).distinct().count()
    print(f"\nColumn '{col_name}': {unique_count} unique values")
    if unique_count < 20:
        unique_values = [row[0] for row in df.select(col_name).distinct().collect()]
        print(f"Unique values: {unique_values}")
```

```
Total number of rows: 500
Summary statistics for numerical columns:
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
|summary|farm_id|region|crop_type|soil_moisture_%|soil_ph|temperature_C|rainfall_mm|humidity_%|sunlight_hours|irrigation_type|fertilizer_type|pesticide_usage_ml|total_days|yield_kg_per_hectare|sensor_id|lati|
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
|count|500|500|500|500|500|500|500|500|500|500|500|500|500|500|500|500|
|mean|NULL|NULL|NULL|26.750133999999998|6.523799999999999|24.672740000000015|181.68573999999998|65.19445999999999|7.03014|NULL|NULL|26.586500000000001|119.456|4012.9269399999976|NULL|22.4424711139|
|stddev|NULL|NULL|NULL|10.15085310012728|0.505552040206049|5.34809567264534|72.03301401550396|14.64204918430281|1.6916704401733542|NULL|NULL|13.200242934344444|16.7980455014713|1174.433039999176|NULL|7.2834017956|
|min|FARM0001|Central USA|Cotton|10.10|5.51|15.0|50.17|40.23|4.01|Drip|Inorganic|5.05|90|2023.56|SENS0001|10.00|
|max|FARM0500|South USA|Wheat|44.98|7.5|34.04|290.96|90.0|10.0|Sprinkler|Organic|47.94|150|5990.29|SENS0500|34.98|

Unique values for string columns:
Column 'farm_id': 500 unique values
Column 'region': 5 unique values
Unique values: ['North India', 'South India', 'South USA', 'Central USA', 'East Africa', 'South USA']
Column 'crop_type': 5 unique values
Unique values: ['Maize', 'Soybean', 'Wheat', 'Cotton', 'Rice']
Column 'irrigation_type': 4 unique values
Unique values: ['None', 'Sprinkler', 'Drip', 'Manual']
Column 'fertilizer_type': 3 unique values
Unique values: ['Organic', 'Mixed', 'Inorganic']
Column 'sensor_id': 500 unique values
Column 'crop_disease_status': 4 unique values
Unique values: ['None', 'Severe', 'Mild', 'Moderate']
```

Figure 39. Data Exploration

A code to show the Basic Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) using PySpark. It is a step where we get an overview of the dataset, like the majority. We can also look at the summary statistics.

4. Data Preprocessing

```
[9] from pyspark.sql.functions import col, sum

# Check for missing values
df.select(*(sum(col(c).isNull().cast("integer")).alias(c) for c in df.columns)).show()
```

Figure 40. Data Preprocessing

This code checks for missing values (Nulls) and counts how many nulls exist per column.

- “**from pyspark.sql.functions import col, sum**”: Imports functions needed to work with columns and to sum values.
- “**c in df.columns**”: Go to each column in your DataFrame.
- “**col(c).isNull()**”: Check if the value in each column is null or not.
- “**cast (“integer”)**”: Means either 0 or 1, or we can say True or False.

5. Feature Engineering

```
[11] from pyspark.ml.feature import VectorAssembler

# Select the relevant numerical & indexed categorical columns.
feature_cols = [
    'soil_moisture_%', 'soil_pH', 'temperature_C', 'rainfall_mm', 'humidity_%',
    'sunlight_hours', 'pesticide_usage_ml', 'total_days', 'yield_kg_per_hectare',
    'latitude', 'longitude', 'NDVI_index',
    'region_indexed', 'crop_type_indexed', 'irrigation_type_indexed', 'fertilizer_type_indexed'
]

# Assemble the feature columns into a single vector column.
assembler = VectorAssembler(inputCols=feature_cols, outputCol="features")
df_assembled = assembler.transform(df_indexed)

# Create the final_data DataFrame.
final_data = df_assembled.select("features", "label")

# Display the first few rows of the final_data DataFrame.
final_data.show(5, truncate=False)
```

features	label
[35.95,5.99,17.79,75.62,77.03,7.27,6.34,122.0,4408.07,14.970941,82.997689,0.63,2.0,3.0,0.0,2.0]	2.0
[19.74,7.24,30.18,89.91,61.13,5.67,9.6,112.0,5389.98,16.613022,70.869009,0.58,3.0,1.0,1.0,0.0]	1.0
[29.32,7.16,27.37,265.43,68.87,8.23,15.26,144.0,2931.16,19.503156,79.068206,0.8,3.0,3.0,3.0,1.0]	2.0
[17.33,6.03,33.73,212.01,70.46,5.03,25.8,134.0,4227.8,31.071298,85.519998,0.44,0.0,0.0,1.0,2.0]	1.0
[19.37,5.92,33.86,269.09,55.73,7.93,25.65,105.0,4979.96,16.56854,81.69172,0.84,0.0,2.0,0.0,1.0]	0.0

only showing top 5 rows

Figure 41. Data Feature Engineering

This code shows how to prepare a dataset for PySpark. It combines all the feature columns into a single vector column that ML in Spark can use.

- **“features” & “label”**: We combine those 2 as our final dataset so that we can start training our model.
- **“final_data.show(5, truncate=False)”**: This code displays the 5 rows of our final data which it ensuring that all the single vectors are visible.

```
[13] from pyspark.ml.evaluation import MulticlassClassificationEvaluator

# Make predictions on the test data.
predictions = model.transform(test_data)

# Instantiate the evaluator.
evaluator = MulticlassClassificationEvaluator(labelCol="label", predictionCol="prediction")

# Calculate Accuracy, F1 Score, Precision, and Recall.
accuracy = evaluator.evaluate(predictions, {evaluator.metricName: "accuracy"})
f1 = evaluator.evaluate(predictions, {evaluator.metricName: "f1"})
precision = evaluator.evaluate(predictions, {evaluator.metricName: "weightedPrecision"})
recall = evaluator.evaluate(predictions, {evaluator.metricName: "weightedRecall"})

# Print the results.
print(f"Accuracy: {accuracy}")
print(f"F1 Score: {f1}")
print(f"Precision: {precision}")
print(f"Recall: {recall}")
```

Accuracy: 0.2222222222222222
F1 Score: 0.22004480277177477
Precision: 0.24586333207022862
Recall: 0.2222222222222222

Figure 42. *Model Evaluation & Performance Metrics*

A code that evaluates how well our data on the test data, using multiple classification metrics. It measures all 4 Performance Metrics, which are Accuracy, F1 Score, Precision, and Recall.

- “**from pyspark.ml.evaluation import MulticlassClassificationEvaluator**”: Imports the classification tasks library.
- For Accuracy, we got 0.22.
- For the F1 Score, we got 0.22 as well.
- For Precision, we got 0.24.
- For Recall, we got 0.22.

These results indicate that the model performed well overall. The Accuracy of around 22% suggests that the model is only correctly identifying a quarter of the instances. Same as the F1 Score, it is very low because of the poor performance in balancing Precision and Recall. The reason why it must be low is that with only 500 rows, a small amount of data, and some of the data is not filled in.

For the Execution Time Comments, the data time is around 17.03 seconds. It is considered fast because you can see the dataset, there are 500 rows. Scalability for PySpark is good, as it allows the same code and approach to be applied to much larger datasets by distributing computation across a cluster. An adequate resolution, such as Spark, must exhibit virtually linear performance gain as the resources are added.

For the Resource Utilization, in the Google Colab, resource usage is limited to a single machine. However, on a distributor cluster, PySpark effectively utilizes the combined resources of multiple nodes for parallel processing. And the Model Performance, most of the performance is around 0.22, which suggests there's a limitation with the model that we chose.

6.0 Result Interpretation & Recommendations

Based on our analysis using the Performance Metrics, we use PySpark to complete our coding analysis and a Decision Tree Classifier, which produced an accuracy of 22% which is similar to F1 Score and Recall. while Precision is 0.02 ahead, which is 0.24%. This shows that the model had small success in accurately predicting the crop disease status based on the given environmental conditions and the features that they have there. The reasons are:

1. The dataset was quite small compared to other datasets, which tend to be more than 1000 rows, but this one is only around 500 rows, which limits the model's ability to learn complex patterns.
2. Some columns have missing or null values, which can affect the quality of the data and also during the analysis.
3. There could be a class imbalance in the data, like timestamp, harvest_date, and sowing_date.

But still, despite the low percentage, it still demonstrates how Big Data Technologies, such as PySpark, can be used for distributed data processing. In a real-life context, such a model could help farmers identify early signs of disease based on IoT sensors like soil moisture, temperature, humidity, etc. This can help them improve their quicker

decision-making and better crop management. John Deere will also use those tools in the future.

To improve future implementations, several enhancements are suggested.

1. Use a Larger & More Balanced Dataset

A larger dataset with balanced classes can improve our overall analysis in the test and training models.

2. Apply More Advanced Algorithms

Use Random Forest or Gradient Boosted Trees to perform better than basic Decision Trees. It performs better than using a basic Decision Tree.

3. Handle Missing and Noisy Data More Effectively

Use Data Cleaning or Imputation to avoid losing useful data, as it can help preserve the integrity and completeness of the dataset.

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